

THE SPIKE PROTEIN INFECTION IMPACT ON HOMO SAPIEN SKIN BLACK IS THE LEAST WHEREAS UPON HOMO SAPIEN SKIN WHITE IS THE MOST

Dr. S. S. Sawhney*

Research and Development(R&D) Division, Department of Chemistry, Uttaranchal College Of Science and Technology, Dehradun-248001 (Uttarakhand), India.

*Corresponding Author: Dr. S. S. Sawhney

Research and Development(R&D) Division, Department of Chemistry, Uttaranchal College Of Science and Technology, Dehradun-248001 (Uttarakhand), India. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18104260>

How to cite this Article: Dr. S. S. Sawhney*. (2026). THE SPIKE PROTEIN INFECTION IMPACT ON HOMO SAPIEN SKIN BLACK IS THE LEAST WHEREAS UPON HOMO SAPIEN SKIN WHITE IS THE MOST. World Journal of Pharmaceutical and Life Science, 12(1), 83–87.

This work is licensed under Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International license.

Article Received on 27/11/2025

Article Revised on 17/12/2025

Article Published on 01/01/2026

ABSTRACT

Homo sapien skin black race had been the only race, defined and conceptualized at tropics with the involvement of high intensity UV rays with life's basic facilities demand and pressure. The original Homo sapien skin black race had to migrate to non-tropics, defined with very lowlevel UV rays with no ability of photoreact with vitamin K epidermally placed at threshold level, causing Homo sapiens to turn skin white at non-tropics. It is environmental effects upon earth only. The layering of melanolipoprotein over stratum granulosum causes saturation in catenation or hydrogen bonding with no space at stratum granulosum for any other addition to step in, whereas the Homo sapien skin white race sans melanolipoprotein gives free access to viruses, bacteria and pathogens etc to hydrogen bond to the exposed protein driven white skin. The spike protein with defined $-C=O$ and $-OH$ groups have the tendency to hydrogenbond with complementary $-OH$ and $-C=O$ functional groups of exposed protein of skin white race whereas the Homo sapien skin black race does not allow functional groups of the spike protein to catenate the black skin as the stratum granulosum is fully catenated and saturated with no further bonding. The spike protein can not infect Homo sapien black skin whereas there are 100% chances for spike protein toinfect 100% the white skin.

KEYWORDS: Melanolipoprotein, Blackskin, White skin, Depigmentation, Desquamation, Spike protein.

INTRODUCTION

Diseases, viral and bacterial infections are accompaniment of life upon earth. SARS-CoV-2, S protein -a virus- identified in 19th century and coined as Covid -19, has been a biggest threat to humanity upon earth and is spreading among humans quicklyworldover. This whole world came into action, identifying it and accepting it as a challenge, but all sincere efforts met failure. In a hurry, Astra Zeneca Co (UK) working on its guesses and intuitions formed a false and unscientific theory onthe engulfment of this virus with the antivirus injections loaded with antigens (dead virus), which had resulted in millions of deaths all over this world. It is unfortunate to record that Nobel Committee awarded Astra Zeneca scientists Nobel Prize. Sawhney rebutted the research done by Astra Zeneca scientists, exposing this falsification of the findings of Astra Zeneca

scientists. Their claims that this whole virus infects lungs only and the antibodies so producedneutralize this virus have been falsified by Sawhney, cautioning the world communities. Falsehood of Astra Zeneca study and data and permission thereon by this world governments and politicians is a big financial conspiracy and fraud, tricking and befooling this world population. The politicising science by the world leaders for money gainat the cost of humans is an unfortunate act.

UV induced Homo sapienblack skin at tropics as resisting and challenging to infecting spike protein in SARS-CoV-2S protein virusis still a grey area which needs to be attendedby the benefits of humanity.

The intensity of UV rays after ozone filtration is notenvironmentally and universally same and divides the

earth into two zones. Tropically defined high intensity UV zone and non-tropically defined low intensity UV rays zone and so the humans species, tropical black skin human race (India, Pakistan, Arabian countries, etc) and non-tropical white skin human race (USA, UK, etc).

Nature had waited billion before evolving humans. All natural species had been genetically evolved upon earth with defined black skin colour to meet out the challenges of earthly environment, with the exceptions of humans who had been evolved genetically with light toned skin, which had inherent inability to tolerate earthly environment UVA, UVB, UVC rays. Nature realising imperfect human blueprint, restructured perfecting the inherent imperfection at post-natal followed a non-genetic biochemical model as explained by Sawhney involving the pre-natal epidermally defined vitamin K threshold, UV rays only with the defined epidermal limits and earthly mineral Cu, Zn etc for perfection of human existence upon earth like other black species.

Homo sapien skin depigmentary disorder and Homo sapien skin pigmentary order have been studied in depth by Sawhney.^[1-6]

Sawhney defined the photochemistry of vitamin K and UV which on interacting release the offspring photoenergy (OPE) with the dimerization of vitamin K. Transduction of OPE to melanocytes, triggers the bioenvironment of melanocytes resulting in the production of melanolipoprotein (skin colour) which gets transferred to stratum basale filling it to its fill, from where melanolipoprotein moves on to stratum spinosum which pushes the skin colour to stratum granulosum, the upper layer of skin making human species perfect like other living species upon earth. This all happens upon tropical regions (India, Africa, Arabic region, etc) of earth defined with about $45 \pm 2^\circ\text{C}$. The human species which migrated to non-tropical regions (USA, UK, France, Russia, etc) remain defined with the light tone skin sans melanolipoprotein due to skin exposure to low intensity UV rays which fail to photoreact with vitamin K in epidermis – the basic point to produce OPE – an important factor in triggering the formation of melanolipoprotein.

At post-natal level, the UV rays impact the light skin surface and enter the epidermal space where the vitamin K had been epidermally placed at pre-natal level. The photoreaction between vitamin K- a photodynamic and UV rays, producing OPE with the dimerisation of vitamin K. The released OPE with transduction reaches and enters melanocytes defined with the inert (dormant) bioenvironment and trigger bioenzymatically the bioreaction among tyrosine with zinc as catalyst, forming melanin which finally catenates lipoprotein as melanolipoprotein (skin colour) with melanolipoprotein formation in melanocytes. The melanolipoprotein migrates to stratum basale fills it to its

brim, then migrates to stratum spinosum and then finally to stratum granulosum – (the upper layer of skin).

The skin colour defined with melanolipoprotein is not permanent. It keeps on desquamating. Desquamation is irreversible. The constancy of skin colour remains defined to its defined tone subject to the constant supply of melanolipoprotein from melanocytes which depends upon the constant supply of OPE and bioenzymatic trigger of the defined biochemicals.

Since over 20,000 years down the lane, the Homosapien skin depigmentary disorder had been observed by Sawhney. At tropics vitamin K deficiency has been the causing factor whereas at non-tropics, the low intensity UV rays.

Tropics is the natural home for humans, who originated in Africa and Asia as black skin species (India, Africa, Arabic region, etc). Due to food scarcity, the humans migrated to non-tropics- an area defined with low intensity UV rays, scientifically unfit and unsuitable for photoreaction with vitamin in epidermal space or place turned black skin race to white skin species (USA, UK, France, etc). Biologically, the Homo sapiens skin depigmentary disorder is not a disease. It is neither contagious nor infectious. The Rishis as per Hindu sacred and holy books such as Atharvaveda, being nonscientific and ignorant of the subject, had stigmatised the Homo sapiens skin depigmentary disorder with its effects down to the generations and misconceptualised the masses in India etc, damaging the affected humans at tropics. The humans (white) at non-tropics have been least affected. Homosapien skin depigmentary disorder has been termed as having no genetic effects upon the next generation of Eurasian couples (white and black couples). Sawhney performed and followed the next generation starting from Eurasian couple.

Sawhney observed the Eurasian couple (white and black skin) down the two generations.

This simple experiment clearly shows that the strategic layering of stratum granulosum (upper skin layer) with melanolipoprotein is not genetically determined. It is biologically event at post-natal level as explained by Sawhney.

The above chart on Eurasian couple shows that the born child of the next generations has been defined naturally with the epidermal threshold vitamin K volumelike the one born out of the normal but black skin couple. The epidermal Vitamin K threshold normally contact with high intensity UV rays, photoreactivelyreact, trigger in the biochemical environment of melanocysts to produce melanin and melanin –lipoprotein polymer (melanolipoprotein) which with skin layer to layer transfer to stratum granulosum, causing defined melanolipoproteindriven skin colour. In contrast the neonate of white couple like Eurasian couple and black couple, is fully loaded with vitamin K epidermally, but under the influence of low intensity UV rays fail to photoreact with epidermally stationed vitamin K and remain skin light toned sans melanolipoprotein at non tropics.

Melanolipoprotein is a catenated of melanin (a polymer of 5,6-indole quinone) with still left points of catenation further upon layering over the Homo sapien white skin, leaving no points for further catenation further catenation. The spike protein, when comes in contact with black skin, fails to infect due to no points available in black skin to hydrogdenbond by spike protein. An infecting part of SARS-COV-2 S protein, studied by Sawhney^[7-9] in details: the spike protein.

Underlying Principle of Spike Protein Infection and De- infection

The whole body is the protein with exception of Homo sapien protein driven light tone which is layered with melanolipoprotein (skin black colour) resulting in saturated catenation.

The spike protein infection is defined as the hydrogen bonding of $-C=O$ and $-OH$ of protein and the complementary functional groups $-OH$ and $-C=O$ of spike protein. De-infection can be defined as the unlocking of hydrogen bonds between the bodyprotein and spike protein by the drug with complementary functions and rehydrogenbond the skin protein functional groups to neutralize it.

The spike protein infects the unlayered part of the body whereas the Homo sapien skin black remains non-vulnerable to infection due to absence of complementary points to interact with at melanolipoprotein layered Homo sapien black skin.

RESULTS

The melanolipoprotein with functional groups layers the protein driven light toned skin catenates with the complementary functional groups $-C=O$ and $-OH$, leaving no further points to interact with when the functional groups of the spike protein: $-C=O$ and $-OH$ reach the black skin surface so infection under these conditions, so no infection on Homo sapien black skin. Whereas the Homo sapien which skin remains vulnerable to infection.

DISCUSSION

The scientific knowledge on the skin structural patterns, components involved melanolipoprotein and desquamation has been defined as basic to understanding why the spike protein does not infect Homo sapiens black skin at tropics whereas it infects Homo sapiens white skin at non-tropics.

Astra Zeneca hurried and thoughtlessly, basing upon the unscientific guesses such as the whole virus (SARS-CoV-2 S protein) participated in causing infection, only the lungs are infected, and antibodies can engulf the virus etc, manufactured Covid-19 vaccine and later followed by Serum Institute of India (SII) Pvt. Ltd. manufactured **COVISHIELD™**. In India Both of which

are **ChAdOx1 nCoV-19** virus vaccines (Recombinant) 5×10^{10} virus particles (vp). These vaccines played havoc with humanity, causing million deaths with serious and irreversible side effects. Sawhney later contributed on the scientific basis on the SARS-CoV-2 S protein study. The spike protein is the infecting factor. The human whole body is infected. The antibodies so produced in the human body due to 5×10^{10} virus particles (vp) in the above vaccines, responsible for the over production of antibodies due to an antigen, could not neutralise the spike protein as the spike protein had been blessed by Nature a layer of glycosylation defined with the no-affinity to antibodies. Sawhney is studying on the SARS-CoV-2 S protein medicine with no side effects. Animal trial is on.

Eurasian is loosely subdivided into western Eurasian populated with Homo sapien skin white race and Eastern Eurasian (Asia) populated with Homo sapiens skin black race. Both races intermix and marry. The child that is brought up at non-tropics (Western Eurasian) assumes Homo sapien white skin under the influence of low intensity UV rays whereas at tropics (Eastern Eurasian), the Homo sapien child becomes black skinned under the impact of high UV rays at tropics. At tropics, the cases of skin depigmentation have been recorded due to the epidermally defined vitamin K deficiency (far below threshold level). The Homo sapien skin depigmentary disorder is no disease per se.

The spike protein as per preliminary scientific basis may not infect Homo sapien pigmented skin whereas the Homo sapien skin depigmentary disorder is fully vulnerable to the spike protein.

Melanin is a polymer of indole-5,6-quinone- a quinone formed during transition of tyrosine to melanin, n being unknown and catenated with lipoprotein within melanocytes probably involving $-C=O$ and $-OH$ of lipoprotein and $-N-H$ and $-C=O$ of melanin polymer with the ability of melanolipoprotein (skin colour) to further catenate or hydrogenbonding with the $-C=O$ and $-OH$ groups of skin protein when melanolipoprotein layers the skin protein of stratum granulosum with effective transition of melanolipoprotein from melanocytes to stratum basale, thereto stratum spinosum and ultimately to stratum granulosum. The melanolipoprotein having of uncatenated functional points with the stratum granulosum is loosely associated with the protein driven skin light tone. Desquamation of melanolipoprotein from the stratum granulosum happens regularly from the complete cover layer of melanolipoprotein over stratum granulosum with the constant vitamin K photoreaction with high intensity UV rays at tropics. Nature balanced the replenishment of melanolipoprotein desquamation. The rate of desquamation is balanced with the constant replenishment with melanolipoprotein – a natural strategic point to buffer the human body against the ill-

effects of UV rays (UVB, UVA and UVC after filtration through ozone).

The exposed skin defined with protein structure with functional groups $-C=O$ and $-OH$ is layered with melanolipoprotein having points of catenation, further catenates the $-C=O$ and $-OH$ of skin protein to the saturation point, having no further chance of catenation. The spike protein attack on black skin is fully resisted because there is no chance of $-C=O$ and $-OH$ groups of the spike protein to catenate or hydroglubond the back skin space. The catenation of melanolipoprotein and functional groups of skin protein is fully saturated and there is no space available for spike protein to step into the completely saturated catenation of melanolipoprotein and protein driven light tone of the skin. This discussion shows that the spike protein attack on Homo sapien black skin race would cause low death rate as compared to Homo sapien white skin races, which are fully vulnerable to spike protein as compared to Homo sapien black skin races.

On The Horizon

The waning and dewaxing out of epidermal vitamin K threshold cause Homo sapien skin depigmentary disorder. Why and how does this happens is unknown to this world. Desquamation does wan epidermal vitamin K threshold but in Homo sapien skin depigmentary disorder, the dewaxing out of vitamin K threshold fails the body to max it out.

Sawhney defined the epidermal vitamin K threshold at pre natal at tropics with continuity to neonatal and post-natal and high intensity UV rays at tropics are defined two factors responsible for melanolipoprotein on stratum granulosum. This study led to hypothesise that natural biomechanism on waning and the waxing out of epidermal vitamin K threshold with the desquamation of melanolipoprotein from skin surface regularly of Homo sapien skin black races at tropics take place. This study is need of the hour to benefit humanity specially app.40 crore leucodermic humans with their full vulnerability to spike protein.

REFERENCES

1. Sawhney, S.S. Thermal stability of melanin. *Thermochimica Acta*, 1994; 247: 377-380.
2. Sawhney, S.S. Cracking Homo sapiens skin pigmentary order, aetiology of skin depigmentary disorder and its attendant skin cancer or cancer and their rehabilitation with naphthoquinone therapy. *wjpls*, 2020; 6(2): 124-136.
3. Sawhney, S.S. The evolutionary biochemical theory on skin pigmentation in Homo Sapien. *Wjpls*, 8(2): 158-163.
4. Sawhney, S.S. Scientific study on Homo sapiens skin de-pigmentary disorder in the light of Homo sapien gut microbiome ecosystem. *Wjpls*, 2023; 9(3): 61-70.

5. Sawhney, S.S. Aetiology and treatment of epidermal depigmentary disorder in humans. Nature proceedings (<http://hdl.handle.net/10101/npre>, 2022; 7025-17.
6. Sawhney, S.S. Homosapien skin pigmentary order and Homo sapiendepigmenatry disorder and its treatment with plumbagozeylanica. RAR publications, 2025; 1-88.
7. Sawhney S.S, New principle-based development of nappthoquinone as on universal preventive drug (coded as GSPZ9) against SARS-CoV-2 S protein and its variants, WJPLS, 2024; 19: 45-57.
8. Sawhney S.S, Decoding causes and effects of covid19 vaccination upon humans, WJPLS, 2024; 10: 124-127.
9. Sawhney S.S, Aetiology of Human Organal Infection With Spike Protein and Its Solution With No Side Effects, wjpls, 2024; 10(12): 129-132.